

**AESTHETICS OF SPACE, ARCHITECTURE OF VOLUME AND FORM
WITHIN ART-RESIDENCES TO FACILITATE THE CREATIVE
PROCESS**

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***Abstract.** Our research presents the importance of the studied theme, the motivation, and character of the form, and the volume of opening an interior space of art-residence type for artists to motivate the creativity of interest groups in different fields.*

The basis of our study focuses on the important factors in the architecture and architecture of the inner space of the concept of art-residence, which has an important role in the manifestation of creativity, libertine and borderless skills, a form of expression in contemporary art.

The architectural aesthetics and functionality of these edifices, and art residence are in close connection with the motivation and stages of the creative process.

Thus, creative people and artists find themselves in their field of specialization in these residences, which offers the freedom of thought to spontaneously manifest information encoded in an abstract and personalized language on improvised media different from the classical ones. This type of concept of art residence is both a creative space and a living space for artists.

Therefore, the architectural typology of art residences aims to ensure, and create a comfortable working environment of creativity, with natural lighting, with an approach of simple plasters from natural materials in light tones, the simpler the better. In big cities, they can serve abandoned spaces that can be used in art residences for artistic creation.

The vision of creativity today is approached through spontaneity as a "flash" from the unconscious processing of information, a form of intuitive art, the art of inspiration. And creative ideas can sometimes be triggered by different experiences, using metaphors, observing nature, or listening to music, a mysterious and difficult phase to describe.

Eventually, the conceptual aesthetics of the residences of artists has become intrinsic to many artistic careers, the freedom to approach space and art through a personalized language, involves the development of contemporary art regardless of the field, meditative and without borders.

Keywords: *interior space architecture, art residence, creativity, aesthetics, artists, nature, openness, experiences.*

"One of the only ways you can get out of a narrow space is to invent a creative space, art-residence."

/Jeff Bezos/

Introduction

Today in the XXI century society and the way of development proceed rapidly and variedly through diversity regardless of country and geographical area, interests, and forms of expression. In our case the research theme of the aesthetics of the architectural space, volume, and form within the art residences that aim to promote freedom of creativity without borders.

The evolution and character of the development of the architecture and architecture of the interior space from antiquity to the present with confidence can

be marked by a variety of expressions, which in turn can be defined as an individual representation and expression of the vision in an original way, different from one concrete architectural type. This fact serves as a prerequisite for the development and evolution of the art field for all and without borders, forms of expression of individual artistic creativity, as well as of the society itself [1].

Art is essentially the deepest form of communication of human creativity, as well as architecture, a universal art of varied representation of built forms, today is the option of open space opened with various functionalities. A unique, concrete, finite definition of the term architecture and art - cannot be highlighted. In a broad sense, the term art denotes any activity, which is based on knowledge, exercise, perception, imagination, and intuition, in the architecture of the interior space, all cumulated in a meditative space, free of sophisticated materials [2].

Contemporary trends in interior architecture are the same as in the borderless visual arts, the freedom to approach the space freed from a load of finishes, materials, and unnecessary objects, as natural as possible, libertine, offering free spaces for various groups and interests to create.

"Art is a huge openness to everything that is possible"

/Victor Hugo/

The actuality of the built space of the art-residence concept

The actuality of the theme is marked by this factor. Today the number of professional artists and independent artists (freelancers), as well as their quantitative percentage in a society, exceeds some previously known limits. This fact forms a cause-effect relationship with reference to the specificity of the art-residence buildings, which represent a new direction in the evolution of architecture, which appeared as a result of social, economic, and cultural problems, as well as the lack of creative workshops, the alert working regime of the artists

from the XXI century, the rapid globalization, the problem of inclusion of the artistic community, etc. [3].

At the same time, the number of residences and residence programs around the world is constantly growing, and work formats and strategies are becoming increasingly diverse. Thus, the dynamics of the appearances and evolution of such centers impose on us the idea of their necessity and the new requirements of society regarding the cultural field. The actuality of the theme is also highlighted by the directions and models of development of these centers in reconversions, revitalizations, and new constructions that impose on us the directives for studying the procedures and methods of revitalization, contemporary rehabilitation, related to the constructive, functional exigencies of today [4].

The process of intensive development of art residences, which today can be observed in different parts of the world, is part of the important transformations in the artistic field, a space of communication between countless correspondents and recipients, as written by the French curator and art critic, Nicolas Bourriaud (1965) in the work "Aesthetics of Interaction" (1998). In the volume researcher Nicolas Bourriaud highlighted the first key points of his future concept according to him, artists are looking for a new modernity based on the concept of translating local cultural values and incorporating them, linking them to the global network. The artist travels through modern and historical periods, isolates the signs from them, and therefore we understand "here and now". He, the artist becomes a kind of nomad in space, in time, and among signs, has a globalized perception, the artist freely crosses the cultural landscapes [5, 6].

"Art must be daily, and public space an art..."

The architectural concept of the art-residence interior space

- *term and concept determination*

The starting point in approaching the topic we researched, served to study the actual study of the term art-residence and the terms adjacent to it. The semantics of the term consists of two words that actually reveal two main functions: art, art, art that refers to the field of study of art and creativity and active function, as well as residence, residence, an accommodation space with passive function, characteristics that form our directions about the specifics and requirements of this type of edifice [7].

Today, the experts have deduced the concept of art residence, its dynamic development, and its changing nature, which encompasses a wide spectrum of activity and involvement. New technologies offer new experiences including residencies in the digital space. The essence of the concept of the residential space, the residencies of artists, which offer plastic artists and other creative professionals time, space, and resources to work, individually or collectively, in the fields of their practice, figure 1 [8].

Fig. 1. Interior space of a warehouse converted into art-residence

The architectural concept of artist residences routinely provides accommodation, artistic coaching, support for creativity, and production or presentation facilities. Increasingly, residencies are themed with resident artists working with other artists, scientists, and professionals from a range of disciplines and sectors, or working in communities defined on specific topics. Artists' residencies may require a tangible result, such as production art, exhibition, project, workshop, or collaboration, or assert that there are no prescribed results [9].

- ***functional and aesthetic elements of the interior space of art-residence***

The architecture of the interior space of the art-residences has main elements of the architectural solution that at the same time serve as elements of forming the aesthetic perception of the space, as follows:

- ***light***

Light has a main role in art-residences, it forms and outlines the architectural form of the existing space, interacts with other main elements form and volume, finishes and exterior landscape, etc. An important role is given to natural light and the method of its transposition and transmission within space.

Therefore, we differentiate several ways of transmitting natural light:

- ***the side light*** is used in the accommodation spaces, offices, and periodical parking spaces. This method of illumination is dependent on the location relative to the geographical cardinal points (N-S-E-V) and also on the visual openings it covers and encompasses. A solution for the formation of a comfortable ambiance is massive and glazed glass coatings, mounted in the direction of opening the natural visual framework, Figure 2. This principle reaches the formation of a state of exaltation, tranquility, reverie, and inspiration and facilitates

the creative process. Thus, the sensory dialogue between the user-artist and the space of contemplation-nature is achieved [10].

Fig. 2. Art-residence with opening to nature – windows, skylights

- ***vertical light*** exhibition spaces are important in creative workshops (craft installation workshops, visual arts, etc.) because of their characteristic of transmitting brightness and the degree of illumination uniformly, without causing a glare effect or changing the feeling of perception of works of art within the expo or workshop spaces, figure 2 [11].

- ***architectural form*** it is paramount within any edifice. From a psychological and aesthetic point of view, within the art-residences, especially the spaces of the workshops, it is beneficial to avoid sharp angles, those of less than 90°, which create a visual discomfort and create a state of restlessness and panic. As a way of achieving a balance for amplifying the creative process, it is appropriate to use simple natural geometric shapes that bring the space user closer to nature and origin, by combining curved shapes with balanced rectangular ones, Figure 3 [12, 13].

Fig. 3. Interior space of the art-residence with combined shapes

- ***architectural space, volume, aesthetics, perception***

As a result of the analysis of the psychology of human expression within the built architectural space, of the aesthetics of the active area space of the art-residences, of the workshops it is recommended to be solved in an open-space type with the easy possibility of transforming these with mobile walls according to the requirements of the artist. Open-space offers the artist the normative, functional space necessary for a free and chaotic, creative arrangement of the machines, work instruments as well as the necessary reverie space. Also, within the exhibition spaces it is recommended to bunk them [14].

- ***finishes, color, materials for art-residence spaces***

The architecture of the built space of the art residence depending on the functional specificity of the interior will opt for various finishes. All finishes are recommended to respect the principle of merging with nature but also to support the secondary plane within the visual ensemble of the space [15].

Fig. 4. Spațiu interior a art-reședinței cu forme combinate

Therefore, for the interior of the art-residences you will opt for light, neutral colors that do not create visual discrepancies and focus the artist on the creative activity, figure 4. So, we distinguish two ways from the divided finishes based on going through the art-residence typology:

- grounge finishes: refers to finishes with worn appearance, specific to the industrial style, loft, concrete plaster type, etc.;
- natural, organic finishes, which refer to the use of materials with natural essence from wood cladding, carpets, etc.

Therefore, the industrial style, the loft style, today defined as an urban one is the most demanded the interior space of the art residences where the old and worn-out-looking finishes are specific to a liberated interior motivates creativity and unlocking and the artistic expression is an impressive one [16].

The architectural typology of the concepts of art-residences aim to ensure, create a comfortable working environment for the creativity of groups of artists, to freely and spontaneously create different, original art.

Conclusions

The concept of art residences for artists has become intrinsic to many artistic careers. They play an important role in facilitating and catalyzing the ability of artists around the world to develop new contemporary art. The actuality of the theme is also highlighted by the directions and models of their development in centers of reconversions, revitalizations, and new constructions that impose on us the directives for studying the procedures and methods of revitalization, contemporary rehabilitation, related to the constructive and functional requirements of today. The architectural aesthetics and functionality of these edifices, and art-residence are close connection with the thinking and stages of the creative process. The concept of art-residence spaces is the opportunity to reuse abandoned buildings, which can easily have a second functional chance, but also the consolidation of society towards creativity and contribute to cultural diversity.

Thus, the dynamics of the appearances and the evolution of such centers impose on us the idea about their necessity, but also the new requirements of the society regarding the cultural field.

Confirmation

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